

Different Approaches to Current Challenges in Educational Psychology

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Abstract

In educational psychology, current challenges arise due to the developing world, technology and access to information. Many of these are to determine instructional strategies and learning contexts related to the learning process for all students, as well as for students with special needs, in terms of their individual characteristics. Identifying the categories and items that make the best contribution to the realization of the learning activity, among the complicating effects of learning, can be a first step in this regard. It is no accident that one of the main theories in educational psychology is the sociocultural approach to learning that emphasizes the key role of interaction in children's learning. If we are to consider students with disabilities, it will be understood that this understanding of interactive learning goes beyond the limitations or potentials of individual students. Contextual aspects that can improve learning experiences and outcomes seem to be compatible with the focused social disability model. In recent years, this theory-based view of interactive learning has led to the development of educational actions such as interactive groups and dialogic literary gatherings that improve the learning outcomes of a variety of children, including those with disabilities. The purpose of this article is to analyze the social impact achieved by a series of research that explores the benefits of such successful educational actions for the education of students with special needs, supplemented by several strategies. As the analysis of data related to national and European research projects and literature studies based on the communicative research methodology also contributes to the study, this methodology draws on equitable dialogue with the end users of the research, including teachers, students with and without disabilities, relatives of students and other community members. requires allowing the creation of an intersubjective knowledge that allows for deeper and more accurate understanding.

Keywords: *Educational Psychology, Learning Techniques, Learning Experiences, Learning Difficulties*

Introduction

The importance of reality and its transformative potential is important for a different approach to the current challenges of educational psychology today. This study examines the applications and results in the literature and practice in order to enable the determination of the benefits of interactive learning environments for disabled students studying in regular schools. Improving educational opportunities for more and more diverse students with special needs attests to the social impact of research based on the fundamental contributions of educational psychology.

Access to general, inclusive and quality education for children with disabilities has not yet been fully achieved. Children with disabilities are still educated in private schools in most countries, with varying proportions from country to country, and these schools therefore have different special needs (World Health Organization, 2021). Appropriate inclusion of children with disabilities in the general education system is therefore part of the European Disability Strategy 2010–2020 (European Commission, 2010). In this context, one of the current challenges of educational psychology is to identify the instructional strategies and learning contexts that best contribute to the education of students with special needs. In this effort, research in educational psychology focuses on strategies, actions, and practices that enhance the learning of these students by taking into account their individual characteristics, but more importantly, research also focuses on strategies, actions, and programs. It benefits the learning of all students, including those whose individual characteristics complicate the learning process, so that shared learning environments that promote successful learning can be created for all.

Instrumental Learning

Instrumental learning is one of the main areas of interest in educational psychology research, particularly in relation to difficulties in reading and literacy (Lloyd et al., 2009; Alanazi, 2017; Alenizi, 2019; Auphan et al., 2019; Hughes et al., 2018). Numerous programs for preventing reading and/or reading difficulties have emerged from research on reading and literacy from an educational psychology perspective, and their effects on improving children's learning have been analyzed (Vellutino and Scanlon, 2002; Papadopoulos et al., 2004; Hatcher et al., 2006). There are also specific studies on reading and literacy programs and the success of these programs with students with special needs (Holliman & Hurry, 2013) and/or students at risk of reading difficulties (Lovett et al., 2017).

The study also explored the relationship between learning difficulties and behavioral problems (Roberts et al., 2019); Accordingly, it appears that low academic achievement is a risk factor for developing behavioral difficulties among students with special educational needs and disabilities (Oldfield et al., 2017). Examination of the learning context and school environment that facilitates or hinders learning has shown that expectations from teachers and their attitudes towards children with special needs are some of the most influential factors (Anderson et al., 2014; Wilson et al., 2016; Bowles et al., 2018). Research has also found that teachers can have a significant impact on the social acceptance of peers with special needs (Schwab et al., 2016), which is important because social exclusion of children can affect their learning difficulties and behavioral problems (Krull et al., 2018). More importantly, there are effective programs to foster peer acceptance and positive coexistence related to curriculum learning, a key issue in facilitating inclusive education (Law et al., 2017; Vuorinen et al., 2019).

Learning for Students with Special Needs

This body of research on effective actions and programs to improve the learning and inclusion of students with disabilities and special needs demonstrates the capacity of research in educational psychology to improve the education of these students. It also shows the importance of the learning context, both in terms of teaching and social relations, on the academic and social performance of students with special needs. This resonates with the social model of disability, which is an approach from a human rights perspective to shift the focus from non-disability centrism and transcend the traditional and individual perspective of people with disabilities to focus on improving their educational experience (Chun Sik Min, 2010; Park, 2015). This perspective assumes that not only should children with disabilities be included in inclusive education, but that inclusive education can be more effective (Lindsay, 2007). This interactive understanding of learning allows to see beyond the limitations or potentials of individual learners and to focus on contextual aspects that can improve their learning experiences and outcomes (Goodley, 2001; Haegele & Hodge, 2016).

Classical Educational Psychology

Classical educational psychology has already emphasized the importance of social context for children's learning. In particular, the sociocultural learning approach developed by Vygotsky and Bruner emphasized the key role of interaction in children's learning and development. Both authors agreed that what a child learns is first shared with others, emphasizing the social construction of knowledge. While Vygotsky (1980) states that higher psychological functions emerge first at the interpsychological level and then at the intrapsychological level in the development of children, Bruner (1996) talks about an individual moment when internalization occurs after a social moment of interaction.

According to Bruner, "Children learn mainly through interaction with others what culture is about and how they grasp the world" (1996, p. 20); therefore, learning takes place through interaction within a community.¹

Vygotsky stated that learning comes before development, not the other way around, and conceptualized the zone of proximal development (ZPD) as representing the opportunity where learning interactions with adults and more talented peers must advance children's development (Vygotsky, 1980). He emphasized that this interaction is especially important for children with disabilities: "Exactly, since retarded children will never reach detailed abstract forms of thought when left on their own, the school should make every effort to advance and develop them in this direction" (Vygotsky, 1980, p. 89). In this context, there is a warning about the risks of working with children with disabilities from a perspective that focuses on biological processes and basic dysfunctions (Vygotsky, 2018). Vygotsky's focus on interaction provides new learning and development opportunities for children with special needs to develop these higher psychological processes.

Interactive Learning View

¹ Bruner has evolved from a more cognitive learning perspective (Bruner, 1973) that focuses on individuals' information processing to a more sociocultural and interactive perspective (Bruner, 1996), conceptualizing the idea of "scaffolding" that enables novice learning.

In recent years, the interactive learning view has led to the development of educational actions that improve the learning outcomes of a variety of children, including those with disabilities (Flecha, 2006-2011). It was an integrated project funded by the European Union under the 6th Framework Program, with the main aim of ensuring both academic success and social cohesion for all children and communities in Europe, regardless of their socioeconomic status. INCLUD-ED has identified successful educational actions (SEA), that is, actions that can increase school success and contribute to social cohesion in every context in which they are implemented (Flecha, 2015). DLG (Soler, 2015; Lopez de Aguilera, 2019) and this issue consists of reading and discussing classical literary works based on dialogic learning principles, and a deeper understanding of the texts as a result of sharing the interpretations and meanings of the participants. Learning interactions, which are the main means of promoting learning in both actions, are facilitated among various people in accordance with the contributions of sociocultural learning theory. In this context, previous research has identified the contributions of Vygotsky and Bruner to be at the root of these SEAs (Elboj and Niemelä, 2010; Garcia et al., 2010).²

Analysis of Social Impact

The basis for creating categories for the analysis of social impact are:

- a) Impact on student engagement: characteristics of successful educational actions that engage students with special needs.
- b) Impact on the cognitive dimension: improvements in instrumental learning and cognitive development.
- c) Impact on the socio-emotional dimension: improvements in social adaptation and emotional/emotional development.

Recent conversations on the social impact of the research pipeline were analyzed by categories (Flecha et al., 2015), identified by IMPACT-EV (European Commission FP7, 2014-2017) and taking into account the social impact criteria used in the SIOR (Flecha et al., 2015), related to improvements, sustainability and transfer. From four categories of data inductively, the following emerges:

- (1) Impact on students with special needs: improvements and sustainability,
- (2) Impact on schools: improvements and sustainability,
- (3) Transfer to new contexts and
- (4) Factors that support social impact.

Views from Educational Psychology

Educational psychologists have researched which learning strategies are most effective in promoting long-term learning. The best strategies involve students generating knowledge through continued engagement. Two of the most valuable strategies are spreading learning over time and testing

² Some of the SEAs that have shown improvements in reading, math, and peer relationships include interactive groups (IG) and dialogic literary meetings (DLG). IG (Valls and Kyriakides, 2013) consists of organizing classes in small heterogeneous groups working on instrumental learning activities based on mutual support and dynamically driven by adult volunteers from the community.

yourself. Resource-based assignments should require students to submit drafts for formative feedback to encourage successful relearning.³ Learning is not easy; students must experience desirable challenges to truly learn.

Educational psychologists have done extensive research into which learning strategies are most effective. Most studies focus on taking exams and are therefore clearly not applicable to the types of learning that some educators typically support. However, learning strategies that can be gathered under the name of "insights from educational psychology" are seen as sufficient number of researches, resources and learning.

A common theme in both educational psychology and information literacy teaching literatures is that they benefit students by clearly stating how to learn. Teachers tend to assume that students know how to learn before entering college. But in fact, very few incoming college students have received adequate training and practice in effective learning techniques. As a result, many students approach their learning tasks in ineffective ways. Head (2013). For example, Silva (2013) clearly identifies students' teaching and practice needs in formulating keywords, understanding the limitations of databases and search engines, evaluating sources, and following citations.

Even if they can find enough resources, many students use shortcuts to reduce the time they need to devote to dealing with text appropriately. This is a problem for authors of research papers, as copying is not composing and "writing" (certainly putting together enough modified bits and pieces to avoid plagiarism) will demonstrate a lack of participation and understanding (Pecorari, 2003). Jamieson and Howard (2013). The most interesting approach to teaching and learning is summarized by the fact that it comes from writing center professionals who draw on both educational psychology and information literacy research. For example, Nelson (1992) and Kuhlthau (1991) conducted a qualitative study of students' research habits. Nelson (1992) described how students faced with writing a research paper must choose between the easy way of summarizing sources and citing a few quotes, and the difficult way of thorough research and careful analysis of different perspectives. Nelson (1992) concluded that assignments need to be designed to encourage them, by asking students to submit drafts and providing timely formative feedback by teachers. Formative assessment is particularly important because it allows students to efficiently learn from their mistakes by being graded. However, many classroom teachers fail to provide ungraded feedback because formative assessments are time consuming.

Related Experiences

In the absence of intermediate requirements, students are more likely to take the easy route and use "sentence mining" to pool resources rather than being intellectually involved in the research project. Brent (2013) argues that to achieve the goals of a liberal education, educators must find "good ways to introduce students to the process of getting in touch with the speech of academics and gradually learning to speak their own language" (p. 41). To achieve this, students need to overcome their tendency to use certain strategies, such as sentence mining. Deeper engagement can be encouraged by assigning reader responses, journal entries, or other forms of continuous reporting throughout the research process. Creating self-reflection activities requires instructors to devote a significant amount of time, but the potential increase in metacognitive awareness of the learning process pays off in student achievement (Brent, 2013). It is clear that the principles within the framework of information literacy for higher education (American Library Association, 2015) are directly applicable to the

³ Students generate understanding by choosing what to pay attention to, organizing what they have learned, and integrating what they already know.

problems identified by Brent (2013). In a more recent study, Brent (2017) investigated the extent to which college seniors accept scholarship as a conversation and describe themselves as having a role in that conversation.

Some students interviewed by Brent (2017) stated that “intellectual curiosity is a luxury that time pressure can easily make it unaffordable” (p. 353). Expectation-value-motivation theory incorporates intellectual curiosity into the value component of learning motivation (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002).

Academic Tasks on Strategies

Academic Tasks on Strategies ⁴ One way to drive students towards full participation, despite the cost, is to share one's own professional experiences. Brent (2017) found that students rarely fully understand the role of research in their teachers' professional lives and suggests that discussing current research projects with students, including the costs and benefits of spending significant time, can be powerfully enlightening and motivating.

Despite the difficulties in accurately assessing the impact of a given strategy on the long-term retention of learning, the evidence for the positive effects of sequential relearning is strong. Sequential relearning is defined as more than one successful retrieval of information over days or weeks (Rawson et al., 2013). The corollary to writing a research paper is to revisit sources and rethink how they fit into the paper in successive sessions, rather than squeezing information into one writing frenzy. Research supports the common-sense idea that spacing between research and writing is more educationally effective than delaying it over time and doing it all night in advance. Not all of the findings of educational psychologists regarding effective study strategies may be directly applicable to students' research processes, but it is believed that it would be helpful to summarize the main findings here. Because educators are often not directly involved in helping students' study.

But knowing which strategies work and what doesn't can work, and the general principles may have broad applicability to the general academic behavior of college students. The first thing we need to deduce from this is the theory of learning styles, which is one of the best-known theories about learning strategies. Despite its prevalence among teachers and parents, the idea that students have preferences for how they receive information and that they will have better learning outcomes if instruction matches these preferences has been refuted (Willingham, Hughes, & Dobolyi, 2015). There are variations to the theory of learning styles, but the theory generally states that individuals have preferences for visual, auditory, and kinesthetic tools to process information and that they will learn better if the material is presented to them in their preferred format. Although it is impossible to prove that something does not exist, “there is no valid evidence to support the theory” (Willingham et al., 2015, p. 267). It has been found that whether the material is presented in visual, auditory, or kinesthetic modes does not make a significant difference in learning outcomes, but instructors must still recognize and adapt instruction to individual differences to accommodate abilities, interests, prior knowledge, and disabilities (Riener & Willingham, 2010). Learning styles theory has been criticized for diverting teacher attention from the more important goal of presenting material in a variety of ways to encourage the interest and engagement of diverse students (Toppo, 2019).

⁴ The opportunity cost of the learning task is the student's ability to devote time to other assignments, socializing with friends, playing sports, sleeping, etc. may be too high according to your request.

Students' Learning Preferences

It is very important to note the difference between learning preferences for how students learn something and proven strategies that effectively help students learn. Styles have not been shown to produce superior learning outcomes, but strategies that encourage engagement have been shown to make real differences in academic achievement.⁵

Teaching Students Effective Learning Strategies

Research on learning strategies has produced a fairly consistent list of strategies and well-founded evidence of what works. The next step for educational psychologists and teachers is to try out effective learning strategies and teaching methods. The desirability of open learning in learning strategies has been recognized for decades in both K-12 (Weinstein & Mayer, 1986) and higher education (McKeachie, Pintrich, & Lin, 1985).⁶ Tuckman and Kennedy (2011) created and administered a course to help students overcome procrastination, gain self-confidence, take responsibility, remember material presented in lecture and text, study for exams, write papers, and generally manage their time. Training in certain learning strategies resulted in students having significantly better grades and graduation rates than peers who did not take the course (Tuckman & Kennedy, 2011). Learning effective strategies not only improves metacognition, but can also result in higher academic achievement. In the study "Optimizing University Learning" (Putnam, Sungkhasettee, & Roediger, 2016) concrete actions are suggested especially for university students that they can use to implement proven learning strategies. Suggestions include visualizing the chronological landscape of the period, reading and generating self-questions about lessons, self-exams, and moving away from just studying (Putnam et al., 2016).

Result

Students who are re-exposed to information are more likely to retain the information in the long term (Carpenter, Cepeda, Rohrer, Kang, & Pashler, 2012). One strategy that can be directly applied to resource-based projects is self-disclosure. Teaching students to produce explanations of what something means to them helps them construct meaning, integrate new information with previous knowledge, and allow them to identify and correct misunderstandings (Chi, de Leeuw, Chiu, & LaVancher, 1994). The authors of a recent meta-analysis state that "self-explanation is directed at the person in order to make new information personally meaningful. Since it is self-focused, the process of self-explanation can be completely implicit or if a self-explanation is clearly expressed, it can only be understood by the learner" (Bisra, Liu, Nesbit, Salimi, & Winne, 2018, p. 704). Guiding students to make their own explanations may be more effective than having the instructor explain, but self-explanatory may take more time (Bisra et al., 2018). The strategy of self-disclosure also has its limits. It has been found that teachers' explanations are less effective if the material learned is an exception to known rules or if students tend to confuse similar but different ideas (Rittle-Johnson & Loehr, 2017). Despite these limitations, guidance counselors and lecturers should take advantage of opportunities to encourage students to explain what new information means to them. Desired challenges All these

⁵ Fiorella and Mayer (2015) argue that genuine participation requires individuals to select, organize and integrate knowledge.

⁶ A consistent theme in the literature on successful study skills programs is the emphasis on metacognition and self-awareness. Burchard & Swerdzewski (2009) found that instruction in learning strategies led to significant improvements in self-awareness and self-regulation.

effective learning strategies require student effort.⁷ Bjork, Dunlosky, and Kornell (2013) used the term “desired challenges” to describe appropriate challenges and responses that lead to the ability to retain and transfer information for a long time.

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⁷ The aim of the trainers is not to do something easy, but to find the most suitable difficulty levels.

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